

RI-VIS D4.3 New Cooperations

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Executive Summary

International collaboration activities of research infrastructures are rather diverse, with different goals or driven by different motivations. A survey among European research infrastructures showed that they have been very active in many collaborative partnerships across the globe. Limited time, resources, funding and, within the last years, COVID-19 have been the major barriers limiting further development of these collaborations. Further interaction with participants of the RI-VIS outreach events indicated that joint projects and interests complemented by personal contacts are important to stimulate cooperation. Research infrastructures may have an important role in stimulating new collaborations as well as ensuring long term sustainable interaction partnerships with dedicated agreements. A template Memorandum of Understanding is included as an appendix to this deliverable. The RI-VIS projects also tested a number of virtual tools important to facilitate matchmaking and stimulate cooperation and provides a number of resources for research infrastructures to use to help build and develop new international cooperations.

Detailed report on the deliverable

Background/Introduction

Research infrastructures exist to enable the research community to use specific facilities, resources and services in order to accelerate scientific achievements and promote sustainable research [1]. A major motivation for the adoption of research infrastructures is an increase in efficiency, by bringing together innovative equipment, data, resources, and the human resources and expertise required to make best use of these, so that fragmentation is reduced, and a wider community can benefit from the pooled investment. This can be seen at multiple scales, from institution-based infrastructure used by multiple departments within an institution or university, to regional infrastructure, national infrastructure and continental-scale infrastructure or even global infrastructure. With each increase in scale, the complexity of further managing and development of the infrastructure as well as enabling fair and democratised access to the infrastructure increases. This can be due, for example, to legal challenges related to sharing resources and data across borders and managing the interests of funders and stakeholders. However, the impact and economies of scale also grow. Scientific research is global in nature, as recently epitomised by the COVID-19 pandemic, international cooperation in research across all domains is crucial to minimise loss of life and impact on global health, the environment and the global economy. Geographical diversity in climate, ecosystems and disease prevalence also provides a key motivator for international collaboration involving research infrastructures to maximise scientific discovery.

Through a concerted effort of the European Commission and member states, and the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures ESFRI, a number of European-scale infrastructures have been supported through initial stages to become mature infrastructures providing vital services to the scientific community. Despite this progress in building a roadmap of research infrastructure for Europe, few of these infrastructures are truly global in scale according to the framework criteria of the Group of Senior Officials on Research Infrastructures [2] for an infrastructure to be considered a Global Research Infrastructure or GRI. Many infrastructures are motivated to explore international collaborations due to the many benefits they can provide, and one of the aims of the RI-VIS project has been to promote and facilitate these partnerships. This deliverable presents the work done to identify the current practices in international collaboration of European Research infrastructures, examples of practical activities and resources to establish and build new cooperations.

Description of work

Existing international collaborations of European infrastructures

International collaboration activities of research infrastructures can take many forms. Indeed, one of the challenges for research infrastructures newly embarking on international collaborations is defining what they are willing to offer and contribute and what they would like to gain from a potential international partner. We investigated the historic international collaboration activities and future plans for international collaboration of 20 European research infrastructures with a survey in 2020. The survey is included in

Appendix 1 and was prepared by RI-VIS. The ERIC Forum project provided feedback and assisted in dissemination of the survey to its members.

The survey started with a background and general strategic section before asking for details about international partnerships already in place or in progress.

General strategy for international collaboration

Infrastructures were asked about whether they had engaged or planned to engage (past, present and future) with collaborators in different world regions: USA / Canada, Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC), Africa, Asia and Oceania.

Figure 1: An overview of how international collaboration has evolved over time between European RIs and specific regions.

Results shown in Figure 1 show the differences in collaboration of European RIs in the regions. From the RIs participating in the survey, Latin America and Asia show the highest levels of historic collaborative activity. There is greatest interest in future collaborations in the Americas.

Infrastructures were also asked about the nature of partnerships they have entered into or propose. The options were: full membership, limited membership, observership, collaboration agreement, shared grants/projects, providing/exchanging advice, providing access to infrastructure services, Other (please specify). Results are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Proposed partnerships for international collaborators offered by European RIs. Collaboration Agreement was most commonly deemed to be an appropriate level of partnership between groups.

The most popular option was collaboration agreement, with 16/20 either using or proposing this as a mechanism for collaboration. Collaboration agreements are written agreements to define a mutual understanding of the collaboration. The next most popular option was shared grants/projects. What these have in common with the collaboration agreement is they have clearly defined activities and

scope. Correspondingly the white paper recommendations towards cooperation between African and European Research infrastructures [3] and recommendations towards cooperation between Latin American and European Research infrastructures [4] both emphasise the importance of formal frameworks/official agreements in their recommendations towards RI representatives.

Options involving exchanging advice and expertise were also popular, with half of the infrastructures offering this to potential international partners. Related to this, options volunteered under ‘other’ included ‘Development of common standards’ and ‘Harmonised sister studies’, both of which imply a mutual exchange and development of best practice. Infrastructure access was on the table for 9/16 infrastructures as part of international collaborations and ‘joint training activities’ was proposed as an ‘other’ option. Where further details were given, infrastructure access was often through instruments such as Horizon 2020 INFRAIA projects or other projects involving delivery of transnational access.

Options involving full membership or observership of the infrastructure were considered/offered by 9/20 of the infrastructures asked. Less popular, although still considered by 5 of the research infrastructures, was the possibility of limited membership of the infrastructure. While the nature of membership can vary from infrastructure to infrastructure, and even between infrastructures with the same legal form such as ERIC, this shows a desire to open membership beyond Europe.

Specific international partnerships in progress

Following the general overview of internationalisation strategy, European infrastructures were asked to provide information about up to 5 international partnerships they were engaged in. In total, information about 52 different partnerships was received. A geographical view of the partnerships described in the survey responses is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Map showing European RI locations and locations of their international partnerships detailed in the survey. Location of the European infrastructure is shown with crosses, and locations of international partners shown with stars. Lines connect the European RIs to their international partners.

Infrastructures were finally asked if there were any factors blocking the further development of each collaboration. In 29% of cases there were blocking factors. Limited time, resources, and funding were the most common barriers to further development of these collaborations (5). Some European infrastructures cited their own maturity as the impediment, either because they were working to establish their legal form (1) or because they needed further development in their own overarching international strategy before fledgeling collaborations could be developed further (3). COVID-19 was mentioned as blockers for some infrastructures (4) both because of travel bans and because of priority shift due to the impacts of the pandemic. Progressing from a 'loose MoU' to full membership (1) due to a lack of enforcement incentive was the issue in one partnership. Political issues: change in political figures (1) and lack of support from governments (1), had blocked interactions as had change in personnel involved in the partnership (1).

Figure 4: Number of international partnerships with blocking factors (left) and relative priority of each partnership within infrastructure's current goals (right).

Perspective on international cooperations from outreach event participants

In addition to surveying the European infrastructures on their international collaboration plans, we asked participants of the bi-regional symposia in Africa, Latin America and Australia about their international collaborations including motivation, key activities and sustainability. At the Africa-Europe Symposium these questions were posed during the meeting using the Mentimeter platform [5] to allow for interactive real-time responses. For the Latin America – Europe Symposium and the Australia – Europe Symposium they were asked in an online form after the event.

The survey complements the previous survey about existing collaborations (Figure 1 and Figure 2) with aspects of symposia participants and their perspective on international engagement and cooperation. The reasons to engage in an international cooperation are rather diverse (Figure 5). Since most symposia participants were scientists, usually involved in international engagement, the key motivation for international engagement is scientific cooperation and exchange of knowledge and experience, which applies for the symposia participants from all three regions. Particularly for African participants a wide range of other aspects were addressed such as community building, funding, access, capacity building, mobility representing a motivation for international engagement (pink in Figure 5).

Figure 5: Response of or outreach event participants to a survey about the motivation for international engagement. The respondents were asked to respond by free text, which was categorized into response categories (for details see Appendix 3 – Results from the surveys from outreach events)

The next question addressed the important step from general motivation and interest to build an international cooperation towards the practical implementation of such an international cooperation by asking how the existing cooperations were initiated (Figure 6). Personal contacts and joint projects followed by events and scientific collaborations represented the key drivers how an international cooperation was initiated. Those points stress the importance of personal engagement between people to learn mutual interests, build trust as an essential element for a successful collaboration. Particularly platforms for exchange are important (see section:

Activities to establish and build new cooperations).

Figure 6: Response of or outreach event participants to a survey question how an international cooperation was initiated. The respondents were asked to respond by free text, which was categorized into response categories (for details see Appendix 3 – Results from the surveys from outreach events)

Once a cooperation is initiated it has to stimulate the partners to continue interacting in a sustainable way. Thus, the participants were asked how to ensure that the cooperation remains active over a longer time period (Figure 7). Joint projects and interaction in events were considered as the key elements for a successful international cooperation. The RI-VIS white papers indicated a number of case studies and projects as success stories within different disciplines [16, 17, 18]. The survey here, further supports the results that scientific goals and common projects are the key drivers for international cooperation among scientists. In this context the role of research infrastructures is particularly important, they provide a framework for interaction between scientists to initiate and sustainably maintain engagement particularly by providing: i) platforms for interaction such as conferences, workshops, training activities etc. ii) enabling joint projects by access to services and other resources of research infrastructures. Additionally, research infrastructures complement the international, often personal engagement driven by scientific interest by building a legal framework in the form Memoranda of Understanding or agreements any by doing that they ensure a long-term strategic planning and enable sustainable cooperation sustainable.

Figure 7: Response of or outreach event participants to a survey question how to ensure long term activity of international cooperations (for details see Appendix 3 – Results from the surveys from outreach events).

Activities to establish and build new cooperations

The three RI-VIS white papers on bi-regional recommendations for cooperation of research infrastructures as well as the surveys with outreach participants (Figure 5, Figure 6 and Figure 7) all highlight the importance of personal relationships to build trust and seed collaboration, however making the initial connection with potential collaborators abroad requires opportunities to meet and understand one another and identify mutual interests.

Matchmaking events

RI-VIS Work package 4 organised, assisted or participated in a number of events aimed at fostering collaboration with European research infrastructures and international counterparts and

collaborators. Due to the restrictions on international travel with the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, the majority of the events we describe took place partially or entirely online.

EU-CELAC Working Group Cooperation Workshops

The EU-CELAC Working Group on Research Infrastructures has complementary aims to RI-VIS, working to enhance bi-regional collaboration of the EU and Latin America and the Caribbean on the topic of research infrastructures. Following a request for information from this working group, RI-VIS and ERIC Forum provided the results of our survey and European Contacts interested in engaging in LAC¹ as input for a series of matchmaking events held by the EU-CELAC Working Group on Research Infrastructures in October 2020. We also promoted and disseminated the events.

There were 4 events in total each around a broad research theme: Health, Energy, Climate change & Biodiversity, Food Security and Emerging Technologies. Participants were asked which theme(s) they would like to attend.

After the introductory plenary sessions, participants were split into 3 breakout rooms in the videoconferencing platform with each room containing a mix of participants from LAC and Europe. At the end of the 30-minute breakout session, the group of European participants rotated to the next breakout room and the LAC participants remained in the room to meet a new group of European participants. After 3 sessions each European group had met each LAC group and vice-versa. For the breakouts, a series of discussion questions were shared in advance to stimulate discussion. An information sheet including the contact details of all participants, information about their organisation, and the type of collaborations they offered, was also shared in advance.

This type of event was very well received by the community and offered the chance to make new connections with potential collaborators. In some of the sessions, the number of participants was too high for sufficient time for discussion and to allow everyone to speak, but other sessions with lower participant numbers allowed for deeper discussions. Having the contact list available allowed participants to prepare for the event by identifying potential contacts of interest.

We would encourage the organisation of similar events in the future and recommend infrastructures interested in collaborations to attend these events.

International Symposia on Research Infrastructures

The three bi-regional symposia on research infrastructures, organised in the context of WP3 of RI-VIS, were conceived to provide opportunities for research infrastructures to seed collaborations between the regions. Originally planned as face-to-face events, they had to be adapted to a fully online format which is particularly challenging for events involving networking. Consequently, the WP3 team investigated different platforms to use which would support networking with features beyond those available from standard videoconferencing software. Ultimately the Whova platform was chosen as it provided features for discussion threads, user profiles, virtual exhibits, meet-ups and photo/document/event sharing between the registered participants, both before, during and after the event.

In addition to the choice of event platform, the agendas of the events were formulated to provide maximum opportunities for the attendees to learn from successful examples of collaboration and hear about opportunities for future collaboration through a series of short talks and panel

¹ Where the survey contributors had given additional consent for us to share their response data with EU-CELAC Working Group on Research Infrastructures

discussions involving experts from the two regions highlighted. More information about the events can be found in references [6, 7, 8].

The format of these events was successful and would propose this as a model for future events of this nature. An event entitled “Europe – Russian Federation Symposium on Research Infrastructures” was held on 17 December 2021, inspired by RI-VIS the symposia and was organised by the CREMLINplus project [9] with the support of the RI-VIS outreach event team [10].

Thematic satellite events at symposia

In addition to the main symposium sessions which covered a broad range of scientific fields, WP4 assisted in arranging satellite events in specific communities.

The first satellite event was in 2020 and organised by Instruct-ERIC entitled “Instruct-ERIC and START: Furthering Structural Biology in Africa” [11], arranged as an in-person event but rapidly converted to a virtual format in contrast to the Africa-Europe symposium on research infrastructures which had to be postponed. This event led to the eventual signature of an MoU between Instruct-ERIC and the University of Cape town in 2021.

For the Latin America – Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures, there were 4 satellite events organised by different thematic communities organised by the infrastructures MIRRI, Instruct-ERIC, BBMRI-ERIC, and Euro-Biolmaging [12, 13, 14, 15], in addition to a virtual guided tour of the Sirius synchrotron in Brazil from our local hosts in Campinas.

At the Australia-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures there was one satellite event from APPF and EMPHASIS “Plant phenotyping workshop - finding common ground and reaching common goals”.

By organising these meetings satellite to the RI-VIS symposia we were able to boost the profile of the satellite events by advertising them alongside the main symposia, encourage participation of key stakeholders such as funders who were participating in the symposia, and provide more community targeted activity following the discussions in the symposium.

Evidence of increased exposure can be seen in the example of the Instruct-ERIC satellite event to the Latin America – Europe Symposium where the satellite event had a separate registration, but also allowed registrants to the main symposium to join via the Whova platform. Of the 122 attendees at the satellite event 85 had registered for the satellite, but 26 had not registered and came from the main symposium without registering for the satellite indicating an audience who may otherwise not have attended the event.

The satellite events helped to solidify earlier activities and plan future work of the respective communities, but also to inform broader interested parties and offer opportunities for them to get involved. Inspiration for those wishing to co-organise similar events can be taken from the agendas of these satellite sessions.

Virtual networking tools

Stimulated by the pandemic, there has been a move to try and recreate online the interactions naturally held face-to-face for example over refreshment breaks in small group conversations. Tools such as Wonder.me [16] and Gather.town [17] attempt to replicate this type of interaction by allowing the user to virtually move around and approach other participants at which point a video call initiates with those in the virtual vicinity. This provides the advantage over break-out rooms that

the individual has more control over who they talk to, but also to explore and ‘listen in’ to conversations. Additional features such as “broadcasting” to everyone and locking groups or private areas allow for more sensitive discussions to be held.

WP4 supported networking sessions at all three RI-VIS symposia using the Wonder platform.

Figure 8: Infographic and slide explaining the Wonder networking session at the Australia-Europe Symposium on Research Infrastructures.

Attendee numbers at the sessions were lower than at other symposium sessions such as the presentations and panel discussions with between 10 and 25 participants engaged in each session. There were a number of possible factors which may contribute to this, including the need to change from one platform to another; technical issues connecting microphones and cameras and browser compatibility issues; and time-zone related challenges as these sessions were held outside of the optimised time zone overlap of the main symposium.

Despite the low attendance, from those who did attend and provide feedback, the session was very popular with participants praising it in their survey responses about the symposium overall [6, 7, 8]. The platform itself was even a topic of discussion in some circles and participants were inspired to use it in their future events.

At the time of writing Wonder.me is a free service, allowing up to 500 users in a space and up to 14 in an individual circle within a space, however the provider plans “to implement a usage-based pricing model (most likely by mid 2022...)”.

Resources

We have collated a series of resources to be used for the furthering of international partnerships on the RI-VIS project website [18]. The resource collection contains first-party resources produced by the RI-VIS project and curated resources from other sources.

[RI-VIS White paper recommendations for bi-regional cooperation of research infrastructures](#) [3, 19, 4]

Introduced earlier in this document, the three white papers focus on European-African, European-Latin American and European-Australian partnerships, respectively. Each report includes an analysis of the opportunities and bottlenecks of European research infrastructures for achieving visibility and developing collaborations within the respective regions as well as specific recommendations for the development of services targeting new partners. With these recommendations we aim to directly address policy makers, funders and RI operators from the respective regions.

RISCAPE International Research Infrastructure Landscape [20]

Another valuable tool to assist research infrastructures in understanding the research infrastructure landscape of their target region is the RISCAPE report: The RISCAPE project performed a landscape analysis of research infrastructures beyond Europe. The analysis identified the most relevant initiatives in each scientific area, as well as relevant initiatives related to organisation/governance and services.

RI-VIS Communication Toolkit [1]

To provide tools for communicating the concept of European research infrastructures and advice for targeting international partners, a communication toolkit has been developed within RI-VIS WPs to assist European research infrastructures to increase their visibility, both individually and collectively. This requires the harmonisation of the strategies, tools, guidelines and resources that European research infrastructures use in their communication. The toolkit also includes strategies to address different targets (private sector, decision-makers and research infrastructures outside of Europe). The toolkit is shared as a publicly available resource (see Deliverable 5.1) and its use actively promoted by all partners via social media and other communication channels.

RI-VIS Regional Communication Guidelines [21, 22]

Developed by WP5 task 5.2, these two guides “Communication guidelines for European research infrastructures: engaging with stakeholders in Africa” and “Communication guidelines for European research infrastructures: engaging with stakeholders in Latin America” use feedback from stakeholders in the non-European region to inform European infrastructures wishing to engage in that region how to plan their communications appropriately.

RI-VIS Guide to writing a Communication Strategy [23]

Within WP4, we have produced a detailed guide for managers of research infrastructures on how to develop a communication strategy. This guide includes an overview of all the aspects that need to be considered when drafting an effective communication strategy for both internal and external communications. This is a valuable tool assisting research infrastructures to optimise their communication efforts to increase positive interaction with new partners.

Survey on usage of communication platforms

In order to identify common communication platforms and gain insights into strategies of international research infrastructures, we conducted a survey about communication activities among managers of research infrastructures from various sectors worldwide as part of Task 4.2. Communication managers from 18 international research infrastructures have completed the survey. The number of replies does not allow for statistically significant analysis of answers, but the results nevertheless provide a useful tool to better understand which communication channels are used and valued as most important by international research infrastructures and potential new partners.

Portal of services from European Research Infrastructures

We have developed a common platform with ARIA to provide information to novice users on how to find services of various research infrastructures as part of Task 4.2. This navigation point of entry consists of a webpage (<https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/portal>) listing individual research infrastructures as well as research infrastructure clusters with short descriptions of the nature of

their services and linking to respective catalogues of services. In addition, the CatRIS project [24] has created a catalogue for infrastructure services which is partially populated and linked to via the RI-VIS website and portal.

CORBEL Innovation Helpdesk [25]

The CORBEL project [26], a cluster project of life science research infrastructures working to provide harmonised infrastructure access and resources across the life science research disciplines, established an innovation and technology transfer helpdesk to provide bespoke advice and guidance to research infrastructures on partnering, research collaboration, business models and IP and regulatory issues. In addition to the advice service, the helpdesk has put together guidelines and templates for collaboration and licencing agreements, confidentiality agreements and material transfer agreements.

RI-VIS Template MoU

Given the results of our survey and recommendations from the white paper recommendations towards African/Latin American and European Research infrastructures to “provide a formal framework for partnership” and “look into signing official agreements that place a priority on long-term sustainable collaboration”, we analysed examples of research infrastructure collaboration agreements and MoUs and provide a template MoU in

Appendix 2 – Template Memorandum of Understanding for International RI Partnerships which can be adapted by infrastructures to use in future international partnerships. The source documents were:

- CORBEL Collaboration Agreement tool with commentary [25]
- EIROForum Charter [27]
- ERIC Forum MOU [28]
- Global-Biolmaging Collaboration Agreements [29]
- Instruct-ERIC MOU [30]
- Collaboration Strategy between ELIXIR and the Australian BioCommons [31]
- DESCAs Model Consortium Agreement [32]
- CORBEL Template for a bilateral Collaboration Agreement between BMS RIs [33]

Key features and considerations for agreements or MoUs:

- Type of framework: Agreement or MoU?

Which framework should you use for your partnerships? The primary consideration here is if you require the collaboration terms to be legally binding or not. An MoU is a non-binding understanding shared by the parties. An agreement, however, can be legally binding unless explicitly including a non-binding clause. The choice of a legally binding or non-binding framework may be influenced by the nature of the collaboration and what is exchanged between the parties. An example might be if the parties were to share financial responsibilities it may be preferable to have a binding agreement. For avoidance of doubt be clear in the document whether it is intended to be legally binding or not.

- Collaboration activities

To make the agreement produce tangible and practical results, it is important to set out the activities which will be carried out collaboratively between the parties. Some examples are given in Appendix 2 – Template Memorandum of Understanding for International RI Partnerships. Activities

can be set out in the main agreement, or the agreement can cover general collaboration principles and be supplemented by individual project agreements which set out the specific activities for individual collaborative projects under the main agreement as described in [25]. Decide which format is more appropriate for your own case.

- What next?

What is your anticipated outcome for the agreement/MoU? How do you determine if your efforts have been successful? Who will decide on the next steps? Include in your agreement a mechanism for revision of the agreement and what will happen as the term comes to an end. It may be that the agreement, if still appropriate, is to be renewed; or it may be that the agreement is for pilot activities and the next step should be towards a new kind of collaboration/membership if the pilot was successful.

Conclusion/Next steps

Through analysis of the international collaborations already proposed or in place in European infrastructures we have identified key features of importance for fruitful international collaboration. We have proposed, created and tested methods and resources for establishing new cooperations of research infrastructures. Through use of these tools and by learning from past events and activities we hope that European research infrastructures will continue to increase their reach globally for the benefit of all.

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Appendices

Appendix 1 – European Research Infrastructure International Collaboration Status Survey

This survey is intended to analyse collaboration strategy and current collaborations between European research infrastructures and their counterparts and collaborating organisations internationally (outside of Europe).

The information you provide will be used to produce reports summarising international/regional collaborative activities and to inform future activities of RI-VIS (ri-vis.eu (<http://ri-vis.eu>)) and ERIC Forum (eric-forum.eu (<http://eric-forum.eu>)). Summary reports may be shared with external parties. No data will not be shared in raw form outside of RI-VIS/ERIC-Forum without your additional consent. We may contact you for further information or follow up activities but only if you give your consent for us to do so.

* Required

About your Infrastructure

Please provide some background information about your infrastructure.

1. What is the name of the infrastructure/organisation you represent? *

2. Is your infrastructure/organisation single-sited, multi-sited, or virtual?

- Single-sited
- Multi-sited / Distributed
- Virtual

3. Where is your infrastructure/organisation located (if multi-sited give location of headquarters/coordinating site)? *

About your international collaboration strategy

Please let us know some general information about your infrastructure's internationalisation plans past and present.

4. Has your RI engaged with researchers, institutions or stakeholders based in non-European countries in the past? *

- Yes
- No
- Not yet but we plan to

5. Within which regions has your RI engaged with/ plans to engage with these stakeholders?

	Previous engagement	Previous and continued engagement	Current engagement	Plans for future engagement	No plans or previous engagement
USA / Canada	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Africa	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Asia	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Oceania	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

6. What kind of partnerships does your infrastructure propose for international (non-European) parties? (members, observers, etc.) Multiple options are allowed.

- Full membership
- Limited membership
- Observership
- Collaboration agreement
- Shared grants / projects
- Providing/exchanging advice
- Providing access to infrastructure services

Other

7. Briefly describe any past/ongoing initiatives your infrastructure/organisation has with the regions indicated above

About your international partnerships

First please indicate how many international (non-European) partnerships you are involved in. Then, if possible, give details of up to 5 of these partnerships.

8. How many international partnerships (outside of Europe) are you involved in?
(These can be new developing relationships or established collaborations)

- 0
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- >5

Partnership #1

In these sections we ask for information on your individual partnerships/collaborations based on the number of international collaborations you told us you were involved in. The sections are numbered in reverse from high to low.

57. Partnership #1: What is the name of the infrastructure/organisation you are partnering with?

58. Partnership #1: Is your partner infrastructure/organisation single-sited, multi-sited, or virtual?

Single-sited

Multi-sited / Distributed

Virtual

Other

59. Partnership #1: Where is the partner infrastructure/organisation located? (if multi-sited give location of headquarters/coordinating site)?

60. Partnership #1: When were interactions with the partnering infrastructure/organisation first initiated?

Format: M/d/yyyy

61. Partnership #1: Describe the nature of the partnership (e.g. what is provided or shared between the two partners?)

62. Partnership #1: What are the benefits of the partnership (e.g. access to data/resources not available in own region, extending user base)?

63. Partnership #1: What is the current status of the partnership? Are any formal agreements in place such as MoU or collaboration agreements?

64. Partnership #1: What are the future plans to develop this partnership?

65. Partnership #1: What is your anticipated timescale for establishing this partnership?

66. Partnership #1: Is there anything blocking further development of this partnership?

Yes

No

67. Partnership #1: Please explain what is blocking the development of the partnership

68. Partnership #1: What is the priority of this partnership within the current goals of your infrastructure/organisation?

- 0 (Low)
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- 6
- 7
- 8
- 9
- 10 (High)

Follow up and feedback

69. Do you agree to be contacted by RI-VIS or ERIC Forum to follow up on your responses? If yes please give your name, email address and position below. For information about how we use your personal data please see the RI-VIS privacy policy <https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/privacy-policy> (<https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/privacy-policy>) and ERIC Forum Privacy Policy <https://www.eric-forum.eu/privacy-policy-2/> (<https://www.eric-forum.eu/privacy-policy-2/>) *

Yes

No

Other

70. Name

71. Email address

72. Position in organisation

73. The ERIC Forum and RI-VIS have been asked to leverage their networks to help the EU-CELAC Working Group on Research Infrastructures to map existing engagements of EU RIs in the Caribbean and Latin America. Would your RI be interested in working with the EU-LAC Working Group on Research Infrastructures? *

- Yes, our RI would be interested in working with the EU-LAC WG
- No, our RI is not currently interested in working with the EU-LAC Working Group on Research Infrastructures

74. Could your RI have a strong, active role in the EU-CELAC WG, contributing actively to the development of initiatives together with the EU-CELAC WG, such as: coordinating workshops, contribute actively to publications, set up trainings and other similar initiatives?

- Yes
- No

75. If no, why?

- Lack of strategic priority: CELAC is not a priority area of engagement for my RI
- Lack of resources
-
- Other

76. Do you agree for us to share your contact details with the EU-LAC Working Group on Research Infrastructures (see their privacy policy at <https://www.eucelac-platform.eu/disclaimer-and-privacy-policy> (<https://www.eucelac-platform.eu/disclaimer-and-privacy-policy>))

- Yes
- No

77. Please give any feedback on the survey itself or the questions in this comment box

Appendix 2 – Template Memorandum of Understanding for International RI Partnerships

[Party 1 logo]

[Party 2 logo]

This template serves as a guide for building a MoU between a research infrastructure and international partner. Elements highlighted in yellow should be completed with details specific to the collaboration and parties. Elements highlighted in blue provide examples of content to be used or adapted in the MoU for inspiration. Elements highlighted in pink are explanatory notes and not intended to be a part of a finalised document.

Memorandum of Understanding

between

[Party 1 name]

[address for correspondence]

and

[Party 2 name]

[address for correspondence]

for

[Short title of collaboration]

Purpose

This Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) describes the intended collaboration of [Party 1] and [Party 2] for [purpose of collaboration].

MOU: Synergies between [Party 1] and [Party 2]

[Party 1]

[Description of the party]

[Party 1] is a research infrastructure for [scientific domain] with the mission [research infrastructure mission statement]. Party one is established as [legal form information] and is composed of [organisational structure: membership and geographical location].

[Party 2]

[Description of the Party]

Aim of this Memorandum of Understanding

The shared interests of [Party 1] and [Party 2] generate valuable opportunities for the two organizations to work together in [area of collaboration]. Cooperation will be established in the following activities:

- i) access to the infrastructure offered by both parties of this MOU in support of users of the infrastructure;
- ii) training programmes developed (or adapted) and delivered in collaboration;
- iii) organisation of events in collaboration or promotion of events organized by either Party;
- iv) invitations to participate in flagship events and conferences arranged by either Party;
- v) joint research activities;
- vi) joint method development;
- vii) joint data collection;
- viii) development of joint projects of mutual interest;
- ix) staff exchanges to promote the exchange of practices;
- x) co-developments of standards;
- xi) sharing of data resources;
- xii) exchange of samples;
- xiii) harmonised sister studies.

In undertaking collaborative actions, the following underlying principles shall apply:

1. The collaborative actions are in line with the mission and research activities of both [Party 1] and [Party 2].
2. The policies and regulations of [Party 1] and [Party 2] in academic, financial and related aspects will be followed.
3. There is clear commitment of both parties to quality assurance of the scientific standards of the programme(s).
4. Collaborative work will fully acknowledge both [Party 1] and [Party 2] in any public disclosure of the results.
5. Each party will link to the website of the collaborating party on its own website.

Funding the collaboration:

In general, each Party shall bear its costs related to its participation in the collaboration except where otherwise agreed.

Additional sources of funding may be explored by the Parties such as joint grant applications to further support activities under this MOU.

You may wish to elaborate here if there are specific funding arrangements planned for different activities or to detail the budget sources for each Party (Core membership budget, specific grant, etc).

Terms of the understanding:

Intellectual property, Confidentiality and publication:

Results and intellectual property are owned by the Party that generates them.

The Parties undertake to hold in confidence any and all documents marked as confidential and any other information which the Parties have made available to one another in a manner that clearly indicates their confidential nature, and not to disclose such information to any third Party. Such obligation of confidentiality shall not extend to information that has become part of the public domain as a result of third-party publications or in any other manner, or the disclosure of which has been explicitly approved by the Party to whom it relates.

Collaborative work will fully acknowledge both [Party 1] and [Party 2] in any public disclosure of the results arising from work undertaken in the frame of this understanding including both data and publications. Each Party should give notice to the other Party of any planned publications arising from work undertaken in the frame of this understanding at least [number of days] days before the publication date. Any objection to the planned publication must be made in writing to the publishing Party within [number of days] days of receipt of the notice.

Limitations and liabilities assigned to this understanding:

This is a non-legally binding MOU. Nothing in this MOU shall be regarded as creating a joint venture, partnership, agency, employment relationship, franchise relationship or taxable entity between the Signing Parties.

Review process for this understanding and amendments:

This MOU will be reviewed by [review responsible] during the final year of operation. On the basis of this review the MOU will either be renewed by the mutual agreement of both parties, or terminated.

This MOU may be amended, in whole or in part, by mutual written agreement.

Entry into Force, Duration:

This MOU shall become effective as soon as it has been signed and dated by both parties.

This MOU shall remain in force for [Duration] years from the data of last signature or until terminated by either party giving [Notice period] months written notice.

It may be necessary to translate the MOU into additional languages to facilitate implementation. If the MOU is translated, consider the addition of a language clause to clarify the definitive language of the document.

Language:

This MOU has been drawn up in [first language] and [second language], in two originals. In case of discrepancy, the [first language] version shall prevail.

Signatures:

For [Party 1]

[Name and title in Party 1 organization]

[Address party 1 signatory]

Signed:

Date:

For [Party 2]

[Name and title in Party 2 organization]

[Address party 2 signatory]

Signed:

Date:

Appendix 3 – Results from the surveys from outreach events

Australia

#	What is your (organisation's) research domain?	In which region is your working place based?	What have been the main reasons for you or your research infrastructure organisation to engage in international cooperation?	Categories
1	Life Sciences	Europe	Exchange of experience, best practice, job shadowing	Exchange of knowledge/experience
2	Humanities	Australia	Access prior knowledge and expertise, ensure interoperability with existing resources	Jobs Efficient use of resources
3	Life Sciences	Europe	Relevance of the research beyond Europe	Global challenges / relevance
4	Life Sciences	Europe	Scientific cooperation	Scientific cooperation

LAC

#	What is your (organisation's) research domain?	In which region is your working place based?	What have been the main reasons for you or your research infrastructure organisation to engage in international cooperation?	Categories
1	Life Sciences	Latin America	New opportunities on research, exchange, etc.	Scientific cooperation
2	Engineering	Latin America	We are the Advanced Computing System for Latin America and Caribe, so, it is normal our cooperation and support for these actions.	Scientific cooperation
3	Life Sciences	Latin America	Interest in developing better opportunities for research cooperation between regions.	Scientific cooperation
4	Life Sciences	Europe	To make the best use of our infrastructure, exchange experiences and work together in areas of joint interest	Exchange of knowledge/experience
5	Humanities	Europe	interdisciplinarity	Efficient use of resources Interdisciplinarity
6	Life Sciences	Latin America	The need for academic cooperation, i.e., sharing information and do better research.	Scientific cooperation
7	Life Sciences	Europe	scientific interests	Scientific cooperation
8	Life Sciences	Europe	good reason	

			To take advantage of geographical diversity in research expertise and specialisms		
	What is your (organisation's) research domain?	In which region is your working place based?	What have been the main reasons for you or your research infrastructure organisation to engage in international cooperation?		
9					Complementarity
Africa					
1					
2	Life Sciences	Europe	Data_sharing		Data sharing
3	Humanities	Europe	data_sharing community_building		Data sharing
4	nn	nn			Community building
5	nn	nn			
6	nn	Africa	Solve_global_challenges		Global challenges / relevance
7	Life Sciences	Europe	new_research_specialities		Scientific cooperation
8	Physics	Europe	Distributed_infrastructur		Distributed
9	Life Sciences	Europe	Local_expertise		Exchange of knowlege/experience
10	Life Sciences	Europe	Common_need Funding_opportunity Service_expansion international_development improve_research_depth		Funding opportunity
11	Other	Europe	connect_Europe_and_Africa		Service expansion
12	Life Sciences	Europe	Community		Scientific cooperation
13	Life Sciences	Europe	ABS biodiversity collaboration		Community building
14	Life Sciences	Europe	share_of_best_practices capacity_building		Scientific cooperation
15	Life Sciences	Europe			Exchange of knowlege/experience
16	Life Sciences	Europe	Global_mission_of_the_RI Visibility		Capacity building
					Global challenges / relevance

17	Life Sciences	Europe		Global challenges / relevance	Service expansion
18	Life Sciences	Europe	expand_users_base cooperation globalization	Scientific cooperation	Mobility
19	Life Sciences	Africa	High_impact_research Mobility	Scientific cooperation	
20	Life Sciences	Europe	big_science		
21	Physics	Europe			
22	Other	Africa	Availability Cost Community	Funding opportunity	Community building
23	Life Sciences	Europe	big_science open_science	Scientific cooperation	
24	Life Sciences	Europe	bioinformatics	Data sharing	
25	Life Sciences	Europe	People_mobility Collaborative_work Learning_others_experien	Mobility	Exchange of knowlege/experie
26	Physics	Other	Enhance_laser_research Construct_Afr_light_sourc	Scientific cooperation	
27	nn	Europe	Crystallography_labs cumulative_research	Scientific cooperation	
28	nn	Africa	access	Access	
29	nn	Africa	benchmaring	Benchmarking	
30	nn	Africa	collaboration networking Skills	Exchange of knowlege/experience	Capacity building
31	nn	Europe	competitiveness excellent_research share_experiences	Exchange of knowlege/experience	Scientific cooperation
32	nn	Europe	knowledge_exchange science_diplomacy	Exchange of knowlege/experience	Science diplomacy
33	nn	nn	data_sharing people_mobility big_science		
34	nn	nn	transnational_access global_challenges big_science		
35	nn	nn	Impact		
36	nn	nn	Collaboration Community_building Science		
37	nn	nn	Global_challenges		

38	nn	nn	resources state-of-the-art experts
39	nn	nn	Shared_learning Comparative_data global_challenges
40	nn	nn	Collaboration Knowledge_exchange

Australia				Categories	Categories
#	What is your (organisation's) research domain?	In which region is your working place based?	How has international cooperation of your organisation been initiated?		
1	Life Sciences	Europe	We met relevant Australian RI colleagues at an EC workshop in 2011 in Brussels, followed by now 10 years of fruitful collaboration.	events	
2	Humanities	Australia	Personal contact	personal contact	
3	Life Sciences	Europe	Interaction at conferences	event	
4	Life Sciences	Europe	National and Regional initiatives	initiative	
LAC				Categories	Categories
#	What is your (organisation's) research domain?	In which region is your working place based?	How has international cooperation of your organisation been initiated?		
1	Life Sciences	Latin America	We do not have an international cooperation right now. I had one after my post-doctoral leave. It is the main goal of our organisation. In fact, it is consequence of the first projects in cooperation between LatinAmerica and Europe in Grid Computing and HPC.	-	
2	Engineering	Latin America		project	
3	Life Sciences	Latin America	Very much interesting.	-	
4	Life Sciences	Europe	Through existing scientific collaborations	scientific collaboration	
5	Humanities	Europe	since the 70's by the researchers	personal contact	
6	Life Sciences	Latin America	Individual contacts with researchers from abroad	personal contact	
7	Life Sciences	Europe	person-to-person	personal contact	
8	Life Sciences	Europe	meeting	event	

	What is your (organisation's) research domain?	In which region is your working place based?	How has international cooperation of your organisation been initiated?		
9			Through signature of MoUs to pursue joint training and research activities	scientific collaboration	agreement
Africa					
1					
2	Life Sciences	Europe	Projects	project	
3	Humanities	Europe	membership third_party_agreements	agreement	
4	nn	nn	Memoranda_of_Understandin resources_federation	funding	
5	nn	nn	social_media personal_contacts	personal contact	
6	nn	Africa	Research_networks Funding	scientific collaboration	funding
7	Life Sciences	Europe	Pilot_grant Bilateral_meeting	agreement	event
8	Physics	Europe	H2020	project	
9	Life Sciences	Europe	Joint_grant_proposals Personal_contacts Grants	project	personal contact
10	Life Sciences	Europe	Partnerships MoU	agreement	
11	Other	Europe			
12	Life Sciences	Europe	Common_goals	common goals	
13	Life Sciences	Europe	RI-VIS Direct_Contact	RI-VIS	
14	Life Sciences	Europe	Via_an_H2020_grant	project	
15	Life Sciences	Europe			
16	Life Sciences	Europe	TNA_projects EU_funded_project	project	

17	Life Sciences	Europe				
18	Life Sciences	Europe	Through_international_org	Teaching	initiative	training
19	Life Sciences	Africa				
20	Life Sciences	Europe	direct_contact	common_goals	personal contact	common goals
21	Physics	Europe				
22	Other	Africa	bilateral_agreement	mobility_support	agreement	funding
			publishing			
			targeted_funding	membership		
23	Life Sciences	Europe	international_partnership		initiative	funding
24	Life Sciences	Europe				
25	Life Sciences	Europe	Contacts	Project_calls	project	personal contact
			Existed_collaborations			
26	Physics	Other	Abdus_Salam ICTP	SA_National_Laser_Centre	scientific collaboration	
27	nn	Europe	International_Partnership	standardization	scientific collaboration	
28	nn	Africa	International_conferences	Journal_editing	event	
29	nn	Africa	Personal_research_links		personal contact	
			Individual	bilateral_collaborations		
30	nn	Africa	Regional_linkages		scientific collaboration	
			research_cooperation	research_infrastructures		
31	nn	Europe	joint_research_activities		scientific collaboration	project
32	nn	Europe				
33	nn	nn				
34	nn	nn				
35	nn	nn				
36	nn	nn				
37	nn	nn				

38	nn	nn
39	nn	nn
40	nn	nn

Australia

#	What is your (organisation's) research domain?	In which region is your working place based?	How do you ensure that a cooperation remains active over a longer period?	Consortium agreement	MoU	Common project	Events	Other
1	Life Sciences	Europe	Annual events, common RI activities, support each other in outreach and advisory roles		MoU		Events	
2	Humanities	Australia	Arranging joint activities, maintaining personal contacts				Events	
3	Life Sciences	Europe	Working on existing challenges and developin new chalenges, research questions.			Joint project		
4	Life Sciences	Europe	Clear funding and clear framework		MoU	Joint project		

LAC

#	What is your (organisation's) research domain?	In which region is your working place based?	How do you ensure that a cooperation remains active over a longer period?	Consortium agreement	MoU	Common project	Events	Other
1	Life Sciences	Latin America	While common interests remain.			Joint project		
2	Engineering	Latin America	Because, SCALAC is a long term organisation with different partners linked by RedCLARA.		MoU	Joint project		
3	Life Sciences	Latin America	By engaging with the key partners in the other region			Joint project	events	
4	Life Sciences	Europe	We have signed MOUs which established the framework for future collaborations		MoU			
5	Humanities	Europe	keeping in touch			Joint project	events	
6	Life Sciences	Latin America	Don't have a definite answer for that yet!			Joint project		
7	Life Sciences	Europe	yes			Joint project		
8	Life Sciences	Europe	further meeting				Events	

	What is your (organisation's) research domain?	In which region is your working place based?	How do you ensure that a cooperation remains active over a longer period?	Consortium agreement	MoU	Common project	Events	Other
9			Collaborate on joint grants and projects		MoU			
Africa								
1								
2	Life Sciences	Europe	mou Joint_events membership third_party_agreement		MoU		Events	
3	Humanities	Europe	MoU		MoU			
4	nn	nn	community_building new_activities agreements				Events	
5	nn	nn	continue_support				Events	
6	nn	Africa						
7	Life Sciences	Europe	MOU mutual_benefits		dum of Understa nding			
8	Physics	Europe						
9	Life Sciences	Europe	Mutual_interest Grants Grant_applications Periodic_updates New_funding_avenues			Joint project	Events	
10	Life Sciences	Europe	Collaborative_projects			Joint project		
11	Other	Europe	funding relevance good_relationships			Joint project		
12	Life Sciences	Europe	Funding Relevant_activities Regular_interaction			Joint project		
13	Life Sciences	Europe	Joint_projects			Joint project		
14	Life Sciences	Europe	joint_activities funding MoU		MoU	Joint project		
15	Life Sciences	Europe						
16	Life Sciences	Europe	direct_contact				Events	

17	Life Sciences	Europe			
18	Life Sciences	Europe	Joint_funding Dialogue		Joint project
19	Life Sciences	Africa			
20	Life Sciences	Europe	communication		
21	Physics	Europe	interdependency relationship_management sustainable_funding		
22	Other	Africa	funding actionable_deliverables social_utility		Joint project
23	Life Sciences	Europe			Joint project
24	Life Sciences	Europe			
25	Life Sciences	Europe	Maintaining_communication Project_opportunities Agreements	Agreements	
26	Physics	Other	Government_buy-ins Committed_partners Sustained_funding		
27	nn	Europe			
28	nn	Africa	participation financial_contribution delivering_obligations		
29	nn	Africa			
30	nn	Africa	Funding Conferences Government_Support joint_research_activities joint_funding transfer_of_knowledge		Joint project Event
31	nn	Europe			Joint project
32	nn	Europe			
33	nn	nn	sustainable_funding mentality_to_open_science joint_training_programmes joint_funding		Joint project
34	nn	nn	common_research_programme		Joint project
35	nn	nn			
36	nn	nn			
37	nn	nn	Shared_motivation		Joint project

38	nn	nn	Communication Succession_Planning Funding Joint_grant_proposals	Joint project	Events
39	nn	nn	Innovative_activities		Events
40	nn	nn	Joint_events	Joint project	